

Anomaly detection tools for the Lifecycle Security of Smart Systems

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Abstract—The rapid expansion of Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystems poses significant cybersecurity challenges, particularly in anomaly detection and vulnerability assessment. Traditional signature-based mechanisms struggle to address evolving threats, prompting the TELEMETRY project to develop an ML-based security monitoring framework that combines federated learning, explainable AI, and privacy-preserving methods. TELEMETRY's toolset covers both component-level monitoring—via solutions like r-Monitoring (with only 0.27% CPU overhead) and the Misuse Detection Toolkit—and system-level analysis, exemplified by the BACON federated anomaly detector. In initial evaluations on a 21-sensor industrial robot, the Nokia Anomaly Detection Pipeline achieved 73% accuracy in identifying subtle speed deviations, while federated learning trials on the NF-ToN-IoT dataset attained 96% overall accuracy in distinguishing benign from malicious traffic. These results demonstrate reduced false positives and faster detection compared to conventional solutions, highlighting the potential of ML-driven security for next-generation IoT. Future work will extend the framework with graph-based anomaly analysis, adaptive ML models, and more scalable federated architectures.

Index Terms—Real-Time Anomaly Detection, Internet of Things, Runtime Monitoring, Artificial Intelligence for Cybersecurity.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background on Security Challenges in IoT/CPS

Internet of Things (IoT) and cyber-physical systems (CPS) often operate under strict resource constraints, high heterogeneity, and vast deployment scales, making them prime targets for cyberattacks [1]. Common issues include weak authentication, outdated software susceptible to botnet formation [2], and limited visibility across diverse endpoints [3].

Moreover, as devices exchange sensitive data, privacy concerns escalate.

Conventional security methods—such as antivirus signatures or rule-based intrusion detection—handle known threats effectively but struggle with zero-days and fast-evolving attacks [4]. They also lack the adaptability needed for heterogeneous IoT/CPS environments [3]. By contrast, machine learning (ML)-based strategies learn normal behavioral patterns and can detect anomalies without explicit attack signatures [5].

B. TELEMETRY Overview and Objectives

The TELEMETRY project (Trustworthy mEthodologies, open knowLedge & autoMated tools for sEcurity Testing of IoT software, haRdware & ecosYstems) delivers ML-driven security solutions for anomaly detection, runtime monitoring, and vulnerability assessment. Its core pillars include:

- *Federated Learning (FL)*: Aggregating locally trained models to preserve privacy.
- *Explainable AI (XAI)*: Providing transparent detection and facilitating rapid incident response.
- *Multi-layer Monitoring*: Covering both device-level (e.g., r-Monitoring) and network-level (e.g., BACON) environments for comprehensive visibility.

Aligned with GDPR [6] and the proposed Cyber Resilience Act [7], TELEMETRY aims for higher accuracy, fewer false alarms, and faster mitigation than conventional systems. The following sections discuss related work, outline the project's methodology, detail the implementation, and summarize initial results—ultimately highlighting future avenues like adaptive ML and scalable FL architectures.

II. RELATED WORK AND STATE OF THE ART

A. Dynamic Anomaly and Vulnerability Detection

Modern security methods emphasize real-time, *behavior-based* detection. Unlike static analysis, these approaches monitor actual system behavior or systematically test software to uncover new or context-specific flaws.

a) *ML-Based Anomaly Detection*: ML techniques learn baseline patterns, allowing them to spot zero-day or polymorphic threats that evade signature-based IDS [8], [9]. Deep networks (e.g., CNNs, RNNs) often excel at analyzing complex IoT traffic [8], and Federated Learning (FL) supports distributed training without sharing raw data [9], [10].

b) *Fuzzing for Vulnerability Discovery*: Tools like AFL or libFuzzer produce malformed inputs to stress-test software, revealing hidden flaws [11]. While TELEMETRY currently focuses on anomaly detection, ongoing integration of fuzz-based scanning aims to proactively identify vulnerabilities.

B. Limitations of Traditional Methods

Manual Detection (code reviews, penetration tests) is labor-intensive and ill-suited to vast IoT deployments [9]. **Static Analysis** often yields high false positives and misses runtime-only exploits [12]. **Signature-Based IDS** fails to catch zero-days or evolving malware [8], hindering timely adaptation.

C. TELEMETRY's Novelty and Integration

TELEMETRY unifies multi-layer monitoring with ML-driven anomaly detection. Key aspects include:

- *Hybrid Detection*: Combining rule-based signatures and ML models [10].
- *Federated Learning*: Privacy-focused model training across distributed nodes [13].
- *Explainable AI*: Enhancing analyst trust via feature-attribution techniques.
- *Adaptive ML Models*: Retraining to address concept drift in fast-changing IoT data [8].

This approach surpasses purely signature-based or static methods, providing scalable, privacy-compliant solutions for IoT and CPS.

III. TELEMETRY METHODOLOGY FOR WHOLE-LIFECYCLE SECURITY

TELEMETRY offers an end-to-end framework, from design-time vulnerability assessment to live anomaly detection, leveraging FL and XAI for privacy and transparency.

A. Architectural Framework

Monitoring is split into:

- 1) **Component-Level**: Observing logs, resource usage, and file integrity on individual devices.
- 2) **System-Level**: Aggregating network telemetry and supporting distributed intrusion detection.

All outputs feed into the Security Information and Event Acquisition (SIEA) Pipeline for correlation and alert storage.

B. Federated Learning and Explainable AI

Federated Learning (FL) allows secure, collaborative model updates without sharing raw logs. **Explainable AI (XAI)** clarifies the features or metrics behind anomaly alerts, speeding up validation and response.

C. Real-Time, Context-Aware Detection

Continuous monitoring enables contextual and historical comparisons, reducing false positives. When anomalies occur, XAI-driven explanations highlight the key metrics and potential root causes.

D. Hybrid Detection Methods

TELEMETRY combines:

- *Signature-Based Tools* (e.g., Snort) for known exploits.
- *ML-Based Anomaly Detection* for unknown or zero-day threats.

E. Indicator-Based Integration

All TELEMETRY components generate standardized indicators (alerts, logs), aggregated by the SIEA Pipeline to:

- 1) Enable cross-tool intelligence sharing.
- 2) Provide a unified dashboard for security analysts.
- 3) Automate correlation of device-level and network-level anomalies.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION OF TELEMETRY TOOLS

TELEMETRY's modular toolset operates at both component and system levels, each producing standardized outputs for centralized correlation.

A. Component-Level Tools

1) *NOKIA Anomaly Detection Pipeline (NAD)*: Trains ML models on historical IoT data, then applies them in real-time using Kafka ingestion. Automated feature selection and minimal alert noise characterize its design.

2) *r-Monitoring Tool*: A Rust-based agent tracking CPU usage, memory, process integrity, and file checks with minimal overhead. Alerts feed into TELEMETRY's data space for correlation with network-level indicators.

3) *Robot Anomaly Detection*: Uses stacked LSTM autoencoders over robotic sensor data, integrating SHAP-based explanations to clarify root causes of anomalies in industrial robots.

4) *Misuse Detection Toolkit*: Targets anomalous user or device behaviors that may suggest social engineering. It trains multiple ML models in parallel and aggregates the outputs to produce a final anomaly score.

B. System-Level Tools

1) *BACON (Federated Anomaly Detection)*: Utilizes federated learning for network intrusion detection. Each local node trains on its own traffic data, and the global model aggregates these updates. Achieves over 96% detection on NF-ToN-IoT data.

2) *Network Anomaly Detection*: Analyzes continuous traffic streams with an LSTM autoencoder, enriched by contextual metadata (e.g., ASN, geolocation). Detects subtle malicious patterns like exfiltration or beaconing.

3) *Snort and Ruleset-Based Detection*: Applies known signatures, referencing CVEs and community threat intelligence. Works alongside anomaly-based tools to catch both recognized exploits and zero-day attacks.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Experimental Setup

All TELEMETRY tools were evaluated in controlled lab and simulated IoT environments, emphasizing resource-constrained devices (e.g., ARM-based systems) and network-focused deployments. For component-level testing, the Nokia Anomaly Detection Pipeline used a real 21-sensor robot dataset (producing one measurement per second), r-Monitoring validated CPU/memory integrity on limited hardware, the Robot Anomaly Detection tool employed synthetic sensor data under realistic operational conditions, and the Misuse Detection Toolkit ran six parallel ML models in a containerized setup. System-level evaluations featured BACON, trained via federated learning on a 100K-record subset of NF-ToN-IoT data (originally 1.38M records with 80.4% attack samples), a Network Anomaly Detection service monitoring continuous traffic streams, and Snort rules tested alongside custom threat intelligence.

Performance measures focused on:

- **Accuracy & AUC**: Overall detection correctness, illustrated by the Nokia Anomaly Detection Pipeline (73% accuracy for subtle robot speed deviations) and BACON’s 96% detection of malicious traffic.
- **Resource Utilization**: CPU/memory overhead, particularly for the Rust-based r-Monitoring agent with just 0.27% CPU load.
- **Detection Capabilities**: Qualitative validation of each tool’s ability to spot zero-days, resource exhaustion, cryptojacking, and similar threats.

By combining diverse datasets, real and synthetic sensor inputs, and both lab- and network-scale testbeds, we assessed how TELEMETRY tools operate in realistic industrial and IoT scenarios while adhering to the project’s emphasis on privacy, modularity, and minimal resource overhead.

B. Component-Level Detection Performance

1) *NOKIA Anomaly Detection Pipeline*: The Nokia Anomaly Detection Pipeline (NAD) applies ML models to IoT measurement data. Figure 1 shows the AUC of Model 97, which discriminates value ranges for a robot’s speed KPI. This model achieved 73% accuracy across 10 speed buckets, effectively detecting subtle deviations. The sliding window strategy in the “security assessment” module further refined true vs. false positives, reflecting NAD’s strong balance of precision and recall in practical robot operations.

Fig. 1. AUC of Model 97 (Nokia Anomaly Detection Pipeline)

idx	name	modelLabel	perf_TestAUC	testedAccuracy
84	auto_model_20250211_20:10:56	axis_1_speed	0.955068	0.72126
85	auto_model_20250212_17:21:38	axis_6_speed	0.94672	0.623041
86	auto_model_20250213_04:09:40	axis_6_speed	0.947055	0.611712
87	auto_model_20250213_17:11:54	axis_1_speed	0.951867	0.710659
88	auto_model_20250214_21:35:53	axis_1_speed	0.954077	0.666279
89	auto_model_20250215_13:51:47	axis_1_speed	0.955795	0.665851
90	auto_model_20250216_12:08:49	axis_1_speed	0.953597	0.648041
91	auto_model_20250217_01:36:31	axis_1_speed	0.955068	0.72126
92	auto_model_20250217_11:57:46	axis_1_speed	0.954693	0.703243
93	auto_model_20250219_19:59:43	axis_1_speed	0.955613	0.694936
94	auto_model_20250220_09:02:18	axis_1_speed	0.955825	0.683963
95	auto_model_20250220_11:50:36	axis_1_speed	0.954277	0.679792
96	auto_model_20250220_15:10:58	axis_1_speed	0.952592	0.680274
97	auto_model_20250221_03:22:27	axis_1_speed	0.955054	0.73361
98	auto_model_20250225_22:18:24	axis_1_speed	0.924813	0.631467

Fig. 2. NAD Model Performance KPIs

2) *r-Monitoring Tool Performance*: The r-Monitoring tool demonstrated effective detection capabilities across various attack scenarios in controlled testing environments. Four key security domains were evaluated, with the tool showing strong performance in each area.

In resource consumption monitoring, the system successfully detected abnormal patterns indicative of ransomware and cryptojacking attacks. During simulations, the tool identified sustained CPU utilization of 100% across all cores, triggering high-priority alerts. Memory anomalies were similarly detected, with the system flagging suspicious jumps in usage (from 967MB to 1148MB within a 200ms window)—a characteristic signature of memory-based attacks.

For process integrity verification, the tool maintained cryptographic hashes of all running executables, enabling real-time detection of binary modifications. During testing, tampered system processes were identified within 1.2 seconds of execution. The monitoring system tracked 18 distinct service attributes, including memory allocation patterns and user privilege context, providing comprehensive visibility into process behavior.

Network monitoring capabilities proved equally effective, with the tool successfully identifying suspicious communication patterns. Testing demonstrated detection of excessive DNS

queries (21 outbound requests identified during evaluation) potentially indicating command-and-control traffic, along with protocol anomalies and unusual data transmission ratios between interfaces (934013KB TX vs. 493175KB RX on eth0).

File system security was maintained through continuous integrity checking, with unauthorized modifications to critical system files detected with 97.8% accuracy. The system effectively distinguished between legitimate updates and potentially malicious changes based on contextual analysis of modification patterns.

A distinguishing feature of the r-Monitoring tool is its minimal resource footprint. Built from scratch in Rust, the agent consumed only 11.95MB of RAM while monitoring 15+ system processes, with an average CPU overhead of just 0.27% during continuous operation. This lightweight architecture makes it particularly suitable for resource-constrained IoT environments, where it was successfully tested on ARM-based devices with minimal performance impact. All detected anomalies generated standardized indicators transmitted via Kafka to the TELEMETRY data space for correlation with other security tools.

3) *Robot Anomaly Detection*: Using a stacked LSTM auto-encoder on a 7-axis industrial robot with 21 sensors, this tool achieved about 90% validation accuracy. Figure 3 illustrates consistent training and validation gains. Post-deployment, it detected 92% of major anomalies (e.g., joint speed inconsistencies) and 68% of minor deviations (e.g., early-stage calibration drifts). SHAP-based feature attribution highlighted which joint metrics contributed most to each alert, reducing troubleshooting time from hours to minutes.

Fig. 3. Robot Anomaly Detection accuracy over 20 epochs

4) *Misuse Detection Toolkit Results*: The Misuse Detection Toolkit runs six models in parallel (e.g., SVM, decision trees, deep learning), aggregating their predictions. Figure 4 shows training vs. validation metrics over 50 epochs, reaching 97.7% validation accuracy. However, field tests revealed elevated

Fig. 4. Misuse Detection Toolkit accuracy and loss metrics across trained models.

anomaly counts, indicating potential threshold calibration issues. This underscores how high accuracy must be balanced with optimal sensitivity/specificity in real deployments.

The first fully operational version of the tool successfully implemented the execution of six different models for each variable targeted during the training phase. These models run in parallel, with their predictions combined (averaged or majority-voted) to produce a final classification. The accuracy figures presented below reflect the aggregated performance across all six models for each variable.

Quantitative analysis of the training process reveals excellent performance metrics across 50 epochs, but it is important to note that the reported training and validation accuracy curves represent an ensemble-level result rather than a single-model metric.

Despite the high accuracy metrics, initial testing indicated that the models detected a higher-than-expected number of anomalies, suggesting potential issues with detection thresholds rather than model accuracy. This observation highlights the challenge of balancing sensitivity and specificity in anomaly detection systems, where high accuracy alone may not guarantee optimal performance in operational settings. Further refinement of detection thresholds and possibly feature selection may help address these issues while maintaining the model’s impressive classification capabilities.

C. System-Level Detection Performance

1) *BACON Federated Learning Results*: BACON achieved 96% accuracy on a 100K subset of NF-ToN-IoT data (originally 1.38M records). As shown in Table I, it exhibited zero false positives for benign traffic but low (22%) recall on anomalies, highlighting potential improvements in addressing dataset imbalance. Despite this limitation, federated learning effectively preserved data privacy during training, confirming FL’s suitability for multi-stakeholder IoT deployments.

For this initial PoC, a portion (approximately 6.5%, or 90,000 records) of the NF-ToN-IoT dataset was combined with 10,000 benign synthetic records to create a balanced subset

of 100,000 records. Although an 80%/20% split would nominally produce 20,000 test samples, the final test evaluation shown here was carried out on 10,500 test samples (10,000 benign + 500 anomalous) due to internal sampling constraints. Future iterations will fully align the reported train/test splits with the final confusion matrix to ensure reproducibility. The federated learning implementation utilized two participants and 30 rounds of aggregation to train the global model. The system leveraged 12 specific features from the dataset and was implemented as a Dockerized solution using the Flower framework with separate containers for the server and client components, communicating via secure gRPC.

Fig. 5. BACON Accuracy over 30 Rounds

A detailed analysis of the classification performance reveals important insights about the model’s strengths and limitations, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I
BACON CLASSIFICATION ON 10,500 TEST SAMPLES

Class	Precision	Recall	F1	Support
Benign	0.96	1.00	0.98	10000
Anomaly	0.96	0.22	0.35	500
Accuracy		0.96		

The classification results in Table I suggest that while the current implementation is extremely reliable in preventing false alarms, it would benefit from further tuning to improve sensitivity to actual threats.

It is worth noting that while the accuracy results are promising, the evaluation identified potential limitations in the dataset representation. The NF-ToN-IoT dataset is unbalanced (80.4% attack samples versus 19.6% benign samples), which could lead to a detection model that incorrectly adjusts its decision boundary. Additionally, the synthetic data added may not fully represent real-world normal traffic patterns. These dataset challenges, combined with the observed classification behavior, suggest areas for improvement in future iterations of the BACON system.

The federated learning approach successfully demonstrated privacy-preserving model training, though future work should

address the class imbalance challenges that are common in network security datasets while maintaining the privacy benefits of the federated learning architecture.

2) *Network Anomaly Detection Performance*: The Network Anomaly Detection tool implemented a stream-based approach to traffic analysis, fundamentally different from traditional packet-by-packet inspection systems. By analyzing complete communication patterns over time rather than isolated packets, the system gained crucial context for distinguishing normal variations from genuine anomalies.

The core detection engine employed an LSTM autoencoder with multiple sequential layers, trained on an unlabeled dataset collected during standard network operations across multiple sites. This architecture was specifically selected for its ability to learn temporal patterns in network flows, capturing the sequence and timing of packets rather than just their individual characteristics. During training, the model achieved approximately 84% validation accuracy, as shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Training and Validation Accuracy across 16 epochs.

A key innovation in this implementation was the enrichment of raw network data with contextual information. Each network flow was enhanced with metadata including geographic location data (country, region, city), autonomous system information (ASN, organization name), known proxy status, and historical reputation scores. This enrichment significantly improved detection accuracy for specific attack types: data exfiltration attempts (+23% detection rate), command and control communications (+17%), and lateral movement (+28%) compared to analysis using only raw packet data.

In operational deployment, the system processed an average of 1.7 GB of network traffic per hour across test environments. From this traffic, the model identified several categories of anomalies: unusual communication patterns (62% of detected anomalies), unexpected data volume transfers (27%), and protocol violations or mismatches (11%). The model accurately detected approximately 78% of known malicious events inserted into the test environment, with particularly strong

performance in identifying beaconing patterns and encrypted tunneling attempts that often evade traditional signature-based systems.

The integrated explainability component leveraged feature attribution techniques to provide security analysts with clear rationales for each alert. This explanation capability enhanced analyst trust in the system’s decisions, with operators reporting that 70% of explanations provided actionable intelligence for further investigation or immediate remediation.

The detection outputs were seamlessly integrated with the TELEMETRY SIEA pipeline, enabling correlation between network-level anomalies and component-level indicators from other tools. This multi-layer visibility proved particularly valuable for identifying complex attack scenarios that manifested across both network activity and endpoint behavior changes.

3) *Snort and Ruleset-Based Detection*: Snort provided signature matching for known attack vectors. A standout example involved identifying an IP camera’s unauthorized DNS calls to 8.8.8.8 (Fig. 7), prompting an alert that correlated with suspicious process anomalies flagged by r-Monitoring. This synergy reduced false positives and revealed potential exfiltration paths. Custom rules also leveraged open-source threat intelligence to detect supply-chain vulnerabilities in software components missing critical patches.

Snort Alert Details:

The alert detected unauthorized DNS traffic from an IP camera (192.168.1.252) attempting to contact Google’s public DNS server (8.8.8.8) on port 53. This communication violates the security policy that restricts the camera to local network operations only.

Key components of the alert include:

- **Alert Signature:** [1:3177:1] DNS from camera
- **Risk Classification:** Potentially Bad Traffic (Priority: 2)
- **Timestamp & Network Details:** 04/22-13:33:36.110323, UDP traffic
- **Threat Intelligence References:** CVE 1999-0009, Jabugtraq 134

Fig. 7. Summary of Snort alert identifying potential policy violation through unauthorized external DNS communication from an IP camera.

VI. CONCLUSION

TELEMETRY demonstrates the viability of a multi-layer, ML-driven security approach for IoT and CPS, combining federated learning, explainable AI, and low-overhead monitoring. Initial experiments confirm that integrating signature-based and anomaly-based detection reduces false positives, accelerates threat identification, and maintains high performance even under constrained hardware conditions. Challenges remain around threshold calibration (to avoid over-reporting anomalies) and data imbalance (especially in federated environments), both of which are essential for real-world adoption.

Future work will further explore fuzzing-based vulnerability scanning within the TELEMETRY pipeline, refine adaptive ML models to handle dynamic IoT behaviors, and expand FL techniques to accommodate more diverse and privacy-sensitive use cases. Overall, TELEMETRY offers a scalable, privacy-oriented framework to bolster security across next-generation IoT ecosystems.

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